

Policy Brief No. 6 - 2026

PROSPER

Jean Monnet Network

The End of Multilevel Governance as we Know it: What is the “R” in the Envisaged NRPPs for the next long-term EU Budget?

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The negotiations on the next [Multiannual Financial Framework](#) (MFF, 2028-34) are in full swing. As always, the central question is: how large will the EU's seven-year budget be? Will the member states stick to the 1.26 percent of National Gross Income (GNI) that makes the bulk of the EU budget, will they increase their contributions or create other, own sources of EU income? Under the heading NextGeneration EU, the 2021-27 MFF was substantially increased, based on debt-financed additional funds to counter the economic effects of the Covid-19 pandemic. The historic exception of large-scale EU-debts implies that, as from 2028, about ten percent of the regular EU budget will go into the repayment of these debts. This de facto reduction of the disposable funds aggravates the impediment that the standard EU budget will hardly be sufficient to tackle the Union's key challenges. Above all, concerns over security, competitiveness, and [innovation require coordinated investment](#) that must also pre-empt regional economic asymmetries from getting reinforced, especially in the Eurozone.

The common [member state reluctance](#) to increase national contributions to the EU budget, as well as diverging views on whether and how to create own resources as independent EU-incomes, widen the MFF negotiation agenda beyond questions of the size and sources. This time the negotiations are enmeshed with a second, at least as crucial, question: how should the EU budget be structured and managed? Together, the questions of the MFF volume and its sources, changes to the long-standing planning and managerial structure of the next MFF have the potential to restructure EU governance as we know it. Concretely, the negotiations turn around where the regions "R" will be placed in future, which will adapt the long-established direct linkages between the EU- and regional-level actors that can circumvent national governments—as

the [definition of multilevel-governance](#) suggests.¹

The "R" on the negotiation table for the MFF

It is customary that the European Commission issues proposals to kick-off negotiations between the member states, which are closely [followed and annotated by the European Parliament](#) that has to, eventually, approve the European Council's draft MFF. In order to enable at least a limited reallocation of funds from the main spending lines—agricultural and cohesion policies—the proposals the [Commission issued in July 2025](#) foresee a fundamental shift in how the EU budget is managed and disbursed. The central new element the introduction of **National and Regional Partnership Plans (NRPPs)**.

On the side of the receiving countries, these **NRPPs** bundle *all* EU funding in *one* centralised plan that lays out the objectives and the measurable targets of a country in line with the broad EU funding objectives and the country specific recommendations the Commission issues. On the EU side, the multiple EU funds for policy-specific objectives are to [be merged](#), with a [new major Fund](#) for economic, social and territorial cohesion, agriculture and rural, fisheries and maritime, prosperity and security. In managerial terms, the NRPPs borrow from the practices developed in the NextGenerationEU payment instrument, the [Recovery and Reconciliation Facility \(RRF\)](#) that branded a [new legal technique](#),² driven

¹ Gary Marks, "Structural Policy and Multilevel Governance in the EC", in Alan Cafruny and Glenda Rosenthal, eds., *The State of the European Community* (New York: Lynne Rienner,), 391-410.

² Fabbrini, F. (2025). The recovery and resilience facility as a new legal technology of European governance. *Journal of European Integration*, 47(1), 85–103.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/07036337.2024.2361830>

by member state demands and evaluated along output-delivery along detailed pre-defined targets. In contrast to the RRF, the NRPPs principally reintroduce the co-financing requirements for EU-funding. Other than under the policy-specific programme funding applicable before according to which decentralised actors (regions, stakeholders) applied for funding, in future, it is not the Commission that will take a funding decision. Instead, the Commission reviews the NRPPs but it is the Council that passes implementing decisions, followed by a Commission financing decision. The NRPPs thus strengthen the role of central governments in the domestic and the EU context.

In doing so, the NRPPs depart fundamentally from long-standing **funding principles** of solidarity as defined in the Treaties that apply with respect to cohesion. They relocate the responsibility to plan, coordinate, implement and evaluate EU-spending from regional to central governmental units and strengthen shared management between the Commission and centralised bodies. In turn, and unlike the RRF, these centralised bodies—probably mostly located in one central governmental ministry—are to establish inclusive procedures and structures with regional and other stakeholders to grant integrated design, planning, implementation and monitoring. In the words of the Commission, this marks a step from decentralised, EU-programme-driven funding model to the centralised NRPPs that [“will be designed and implemented in close partnership with national and regional authorities and relevant stakeholders”](#). How this objective of an inclusive and interactive national programme design and management can be achieved is presently taking shape in the member states. This happens under conditions of multiple uncertainties and without much prior experience to build on.

First, negotiating the new NRPP-model before having clarity of the volume of the MFF poses a host of questions. The

future MFF bundles “new” and “old” priorities in separate headings (two are of relevance here, 1: cohesion, regional, agricultural policy – with a decreased amount, 2: competitiveness, prosperity and security with a 17% increase), to enable member states also to reallocate parts of resources according to national needs. While the Commission’s proposals ringfences certain amounts of the MFF for cohesion and the other spending lines, it creates national discretion for how these funds are attributed to the regional level. Thus, while it is still unclear how much money will be in each heading in absolute terms, the NRPP model must be shaped. Even though certain amounts should be ringfenced (i.e. certain percentages in the NRPP must cover certain broader objectives), without knowledge about the actual MFF volume (anything between a drop to 10% less than before to a rise to an unknown level with the addition of new EU own resources), devising national programme goals and shares is to a great degree a hypothetical exercise for the regional authorities and stakeholders who cannot estimate whether the model will bear funds or not.

Second, how regional authorities and stakeholders are integrated will depend greatly on the internal member state organisation. In fact, the national systems do not have established structures or practices of how to co-author, co-manage, and co-evaluate detailed funding targets to the extent the new model foresees it. Notably, the NRPPs are to bring together newly established central planning units with national and regional authorities as well as stakeholders under conditions of new zero-sum calculations the MFF creates. Especially federal states face hands-on challenges on how to integrate multiple veto-players, not least in the enforcement of the NRPPs. The envisaged decrease in the envelope for cohesion funding and the leeway granted to member states to

relocate funds according to nationally defined priorities, inevitably implies trade-offs between cohesion and other long-standing as well as new objectives. Additionally, and more relevantly, conflicts should be foreseen also between regional authorities. Whereas the EU-programme driven funding tackled cohesion by distributing money primarily to the relatively weakest regions, the national definition of targets means that conflicts over disbursement are to be fought out among regions in each country, including regional demands for national compensation for lost EU-funding. Who will get what in the NRPPs is exactly what the NRPPs should determine: a stronger emphasis on competitiveness promises to relocate money away from relatively weaker to stronger regions, a guarantee for farmers not to reduce funding will imply cuts in cohesion—and so forth. Already the build-up of how to write an NRPP is frontloaded with redistributive conflicts suggesting that centralised, less-inclusive decision-making might be the only viable way to finalise an NRPP.

Third, in light of upcoming elections, pressure is high to complete the MFF negotiations soon. To pre-empt additional uncertainties about the composition of the Council, the ambition is to complete negotiations by the end of 2026—meaning that the national NRPP drafting frameworks need to be completed by mid 2026 to move on to start negotiating the MFF volume. In addition, the countries need to submit their final NRPPs by 31 January 2028. In light of the above outlined likely complexities, it will take some time to draft NRPPs with clear and measurable milestones and targets, which do not only incorporate horizontal EU standards but need to define achievable benchmarks, backed by co-funding guarantees and sound implementation plans to pre-empt a failure of target achievement. Hence, creating the frameworks for drafting the NRPPs has to be realised extremely quickly,

limiting naturally the scope for a comprehensive inclusive procedure already at this stage.

In essence, under high-pitched time pressure we are witnessing an ad hoc, strongly idiosyncratic learning-by-doing approach to come up with 27 programming infrastructures to draft the NRPPs. This happens for a widened EU agenda in form of headings with financial envelopes, but without knowledge about how much each envelope will contain. The looming pressure that new, pressing challenges need financial means is high, while long-standing agricultural and cohesion objectives remain imperative considering the potential costs uncontrollable economic asymmetries can produce in the common economic and monetary union, not to mention the values of solidarity and unity the union rests on but risks to counteract by opening the competition over EU resources in the domestic realm.

Relocating Multilevel Governance into National Planning

Critics, such as the European Parliament in its [interim report](#) on the proposed [MFF Council Regulation](#), argue with respect to the aligned [proposal for the NRPP](#) “that the ‘one plan per Member State’ approach implicitly erodes the European dimension of the EU budget and the objectives of common EU policies, leads to excessive centralisation challenging the principles of subsidiarity and proportionality, excludes regional and local authorities and relevant stakeholders from a meaningful role in shaping priorities, and undermines multilevel governance and the territorial dimension of spending” (Article 22). In addition, the NRPP model builds on the performance-based budgeting of the RRF without clear solutions on how to remedy [weaknesses of the approach](#)³

³ See e.g. European Court of Auditors, review 02/2025: “Performance-orientation, accountability and transparency – lessons to be learned from the weaknesses of the RRF”, Publications Office of the European Union, 2025.

in the adapted shared management set-up.

This notwithstanding, [shortcomings of the cohesion spending system](#)⁴ as well as the pressure to reallocate recourses persist. A [Bruegel analysis](#)⁵ comes, overall, to the positive evaluation “that the NRPP structure is conceptually sound”. In particular the integration of various policy areas into a single plan is seen as a plus as this measure reduces the well-known problems of overlaps and failures to coordinate the various actions. Accordingly, the “selective reduction of cohesion funding is justifiable”, and identifies scope to improve the performance-based budgeting. This assessment is based on a crucial positioning on cohesion policy, namely that “[s]ub-national cohesion spending should be made conditional on national reform only if such reforms have beneficial local impacts or generate cross-border benefits”. While Bruegel’s and [other](#) analyses share the European Parliament’s critique of insufficient parliamentary oversight, the analysis argues that the performance-based NRPPs should shift more authority from the sub-national to the national level. In addition, it calls for a “robust methodology [...] to ensure milestones and targets are sufficiently ambitious”, which does necessitate “deep local knowledge, independent evaluators – distinct from beneficiaries and free of conflicts of interest”.

The apparently contrasting conclusions of these exemplary analyses by the European Parliament and the authors of the Bruegel report

⁴ See e.g. European Court of Auditors, review 03/2024: “An overview of the assurance framework and the key factors contributing to errors in 2014-2020 cohesion spending”, Publications Office of the European Union, 2024.

⁵ Darvas, Z., M.S. Lappe, B. Sangers and J. Zettelmeyer (2026) ‘National plans, regional voices: cohesion policy in the next European Union budget’, Policy Brief 06/2026, Bruegel, available at <https://doi.org/10.64153/UDNN6182>

merit two comments. On the one hand, the call to focus cohesion openly on issues of cross-border impact only and, thus, change the scope of EU cohesion policy may be understood as an honest reading of the NRPP proposals’ subtext. It implies that the European Parliament firmly rejects a possible [renationalisation](#). As it stands, [merely ringfencing certain amounts](#) for cohesion creates the risk that the Treaty objective to reduce regional disparities will be marginalised rather than becoming a shared domestic objective in the spirit of subsidiarity. On the other hand, the call to improve the managerial fine-tuning to define and assess targets and milestones subscribes principally to the RRF model, which runs without the “R” for “Regional”, suggesting that incorporating local, regional and other stakeholders into shared management will remedy the known managerial and oversight shortcomings. Ideally, the exclusion of regional actors from programming and management, as had previously applied in the old cohesion-funding schemes, will be replaced by a full integration of a host of actors in a new model of highly interactive and inclusive [shared management](#). Essentially, all multilevel interaction would happen in a continuous joint endeavour of drafting, implementing and assessing the NRPPs, with clear targets and milestones serving as rails to structure the administratively demanding procedures.

The current emphasis on integrating regional authorities and stakeholders in the NRPP framework is thus to remedy both the managerial shortcomings of cohesion policy and the RRF in an unprecedented cooperative framework that each member state establishes idiosyncratically. Beyond the technical challenges discussed above, the NRPP framework urges more fundamental questions about the inevitably much more encompassing shared management requirements. Despite the merits that demand-driven and performance-based budgeting offer in

overcoming the unquestionable weaknesses of cohesion policy, the NRPPs' approach to create inclusive national participation at all stages will not only create hard competition over the reallocation of resources among regions and stakeholder groups, it will also undermine the more general goal to achieve more coherent centralised steering. Trade-offs in centralised coherence and fully inclusive processes are evident; they must inevitably incorporate hefty redistribution conflicts into the NRPPs. In addition, the NRPP model undermines the EU-level steering capacity. Even though the Commission gains considerably more access and oversight functions, it actually loses the power to decide over the allocation of funds because it is the Council that approves the NRPPs. Only if the NRPPs manage to create a highly cooperative conflict resolution framework, that can distinguish how resources are "best" allocated, can the interactive and shared management system flourish.

Frankly, this vision seems to underestimate the role of politics and the high stakes of redistribution. Given the incentive that the NRPP will redistribute funds, the model somehow suggests that those who will lose in the process of reallocation will subscribe to these changes in the inclusive process—which may realistically lead to solutions that sideline certain claims for cohesion. Politically and pragmatically, a centralisation of decision-making and a streamlining of shared management to become a direct exchange between the centralised national (decision-making) unit and the Commission appear more realistic—rendering the NRPP into, at best an "NrPP" that could easily crowd out regional authorities. The NRPPs end multilevel governance that circumvented national governments and suggests, instead, to firmly integrate multilevel shared management into national structures. A constant exchange over target achievement does not remedy the fact that the new infrastructure does not

take a step towards fiscal federalism but, instead, strengthens the Council's role. In combination with insufficient parliamentary oversight both at EU and member state levels, the Commission remains too weak to really allocate funds based on self-reported measurable performance—except, maybe, for the most glaring disrespect of super-milestones on the rule of law that a majority of member states want to sanction. In essence, the NRPPs may develop into an attractive model for the 27 central executives to steer EU budgeting at times when sources for investment are scarce but bitterly needed. The model offers few real safeguards that the funding will still be strong in steering clear-cut EU objectives across 27 states and will therefore be perceived by citizens as a value added by the EU.

This policy brief is based on the in-depth analysis Heidbreder, E. G. (2025). Rebalancing the European Union's authority by fiscal integration: the commission's changed role in multilevel governance. *Journal of European Public Policy*, 1–23. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13501763.2025.2587926>

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